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Abstract

Technical education plays a major role in the field of higher education in Sri Lanka. The expansion of the technical education sector was slow during the first half of the 20th century due to the limited demand for technical skills generated in the colonial economy. However, since the independence this sector has received a high priority. Technical education can be regarded as one of the avenues to get foreign technology transferred into Sri Lanka through foreign grants for technical corporation. Under technical corporation grants, generally, foreign countries come into agreements to provide physical facilities, assistance to develop training programmes, training materials, training for local staff, etc. for an agreed time period. Though the agreed grant period of some of the technical corporation programmes now elapsed, training programmes that had developed are still running. The evidence reveals that the increased demand for the technical education programmes has been mainly due to the fact that the universities have not been able to meet the demand for job-oriented technical education.

The aim of the paper is to investigate technical training programmes that were initiated through technical corporation grants to assess appropriateness and effectiveness of the programmes. For the study, an analytical model was developed and equivalent technical training programmes, where agreed grant period elapsed were selected. Data was collected through questionnaires and interviews. The investigation revealed that in all the technical training programmes, both donors and recipients mainly concerned with buildings, vehicles, machinery, etc. and less concerned with the training of trainers, technology upgrading channels, arrangement of institute management procedures, etc.

1. Introduction

There is an ample evidence to indicate that technology play a major role in creating wealth of nations. A country should have a socially relevant and technically sound technical education system. In that system, a candidate who successfully complete a technical training programme in any occupational level in technical production, maintenance, services and research and development need a mix of skills, manipulative techniques and knowledge. It is the proportion of this skill mix that determines the technical occupational level. For adequate education-occupation linkage, technical education should consist of three basic components of engineering, i.e., skills of manipulative techniques (what), knowledge of engineering processes (how) and knowledge of corresponding scientific principles (why). In the contemporary industrialized society, the technical education system requires continual review and upgrading to meet the technological changes and also provision for effective linkages with industry and newer technologies.

The technological advancement through innovations and research and development are much expensive methods to acquire modern technology to less technologically developed countries like Sri Lanka. One of the suitable methods to acquire modern technology to a less technologically developed country is through foreign technology transfer. The technical education is one of the key windows in acquiring foreign technology to Sri Lanka through foreign grants for technical corporation. Under technical corporation grants, generally, foreign countries come into agreements to provide physical facilities, assistance to develop training programmes, training materials, training for local staff, etc. for an agreed time period. Such technical corporation grants can be categorized into two. First category is designing and developing programmes and upgrading knowledge of academic staff of the technical training institutes. Second category is improving physical facilities of the technical training institutions. Several countries involve in providing technical corporation grants for either one of the above categories. Only few countries, however, involve in providing technical corporation grants for both of the above categories.

In Sri Lankan higher education sector technical education plays a major role. The expansion of the technical education sector was slow during the first half of the 20th century due to the limited demand for technical skills generated in the colonial economy. However, since the independence this sector has received a high priority. In general, there are various problems in the Sri Lankan technical education sector related to knowledge, skills and abilities at technicians and craftsmen level; the trainees if technical training institutes, who had successfully completed the programmes face difficulties in securing employment opportunities. However, the evidence reveals that the increased demand for the technical education programmes has been mainly due to the fact that the universities have not been able to meet the demand for job-oriented technical education. Further, the preliminary investigations revealed that though the agreed grant period of some of the technical corporation programmes now elapsed, training programmes that had developed are still running. The aim of this paper is to investigate the technical training programmes totally funded (covering two categories mentioned above) through technical corporation grants to assess appropriateness and effectiveness of the programmes.

2. Technical education

2.1. Standard Occupational Levels in the Technical/Engineering Education

There are four occupation levels in the technical/engineering education.

2.1.1. First Level

Primary manual skills are applied on production machines, construction work or work with various kinds of tools, etc., which are repetitive along with knowledge needed for understanding the processes involved and the functions of equipment and tools used. Some manipulative techniques are also needed at this level to meet the skill requirements of emerging technologies and job oriented skill integration for higher efficiency. This level has many occupation titles such as turner, machinist, fitter, welder, electrician, and electronic mechanic. This level could be identified as the craft certificate level.

2.1.2. Second Level

The education/training component for this level is judicious mix knowledge of manipulative skills and basic exposure to the technological and engineering processes to understand technological processes involved in production, services or maintenance. This understanding is important in the supervision of production line and in maintenance shops. The skills, knowledge and abilities obtain at this level can be used to apply technology to field operations in production and construction; test, develop, install and run engineering plants; draft and design production line projects; estimate costs for customers in the use of engineering or scientific equipment; liaison between engineer and skilled workers to interpret plans and designs, determine production and construction techniques, choosing tools and machines suitable for each object, supervision of skilled workers and to assist engineers in design work and in laboratories. This second level is also corresponds as middle-level technical personnel because it is between the first and the third. There are many occupation titles in this level depending on the individual function or cluster of functions performed, such as technicians, supervisor, foreman, overseer, section officer, and junior engineer.

2.1.3. Third Level

Often, in developing countries the third or the technician-level education is a more diluted form of a degree programme rather than a well-focused occupational programme. Design and execution of engineering projects, and application of scientific knowledge in products and services are some of the important responsibilities at this level which require a higher degree of qualitative and analytical responsibilities. Thus, this level provides skills to design and develop products and processes; design engineering plants and equipment; plan and design manufacturing industries, electrical power systems, hydraulic structures, buildings, highways and bridges, railways, and public health systems.

2.1.4. Fourth Level

This level is regarded as that of a professional engineer or technologist with a variety of positions and titles. The education/training component of this level corresponds to a degree or a postgraduate degree in engineering or technology. In this level skills are

formed in the areas of engineering and applied science research; R & D, with the objective of marketing technical innovation, design and development; R & D for updating and the development of technology.

This stratified structure of the technical and engineering levels is, however, not absolute. There are overlapping areas between the different levels, especially such overlapping can be identified between the first and second levels and the second and third levels depending on the state and the level of technology in a country and how it is applied and managed in different organizations.

3. Methodology

3.1. Sample of the Study

As previously mentioned, technical corporation grants for technical education sector can be divided into two categories. Some are targeted to develop and design training programmes and to upgrade knowledge of technical staff members while some are targeted to improve physical facilities of technical training institutions. Several countries provide technical corporation grants either to develop and design training programmes and to upgrade knowledge of technical staff members or to improve physical facilities of technical training institutions. In such cases, the effect of grants to the technical education is difficult to analyze. To overcome this difficulty, it was decided to select technical training institutions to which technical corporation grants are provided to cover both of these categories. The study was further narrowed down to investigate technical training programmes that come under third or technician level of the four technical occupation levels discussed in section 2.1.

For the study, four technical training establishments of which two were totally funded by Germany and another two totally funded by Japan had been selected. To enable comparisons to be made it was decided to select equivalent training programmes conducted by these four institutions. Thus from each of these institution, third level or the main technical training programme was selected. In three of the institutions, the programmes selected come under the specialised area of automobile while in the fourth institute the programme selected come under the specialised area of the maintenance of construction equipment. In all the selected institutions/programmes, the agreed grant period had already elapsed. The two institutions totally funded by Germany were identified as “A” and “B”. The two institutions totally funded by Japan were identified as “C” and “D”.

3.1.1. Description of the Training Institutes and Training Programmes Selected

Technical Training Institute A

The training institute established in several decades ago. Germany supplied equipment for the workshop, machines and tools, textbooks and other technical aids as well as teaching and technical staff for three year period. Sri Lanka provided land, buildings, maintenance cost, administrative and technical staff for the training institute. After the initial grant period elapsed, in two occasions further expansion agreements were signed. Few decades ago the final grant period elapsed. However time to time training institute received further aid to up grade the training programmes from Germany.

With regard to the structure of the training programme selected, the total duration is four years. In the first year, trainees undergo basic workshop practice and theory on workshop practice. During the next two years trainees are given industrial placements in their chosen specialization field in the automobile. The specialized fields are automobile mechanics, mechanist, welders, tinkers, and auto electricians. In the final year trainees are sent for in-plant training.

Technical Training Institute B

The training institute established during the 1990s with the collaboration of a German training institute, catering for automobile engineering industry. This training programme was designed and developed with the help of the training institute of Germany. In mid 1990s grant period elapsed. But Sri Lankan training institute is still linked to the German training institute and cared for in continuous technology upgrading. Time to time through German training institute, Sri Lankan institute send their training officers to Germany as well as to India and Singapore for further training. In addition, German training institute send training materials including CDs, Videos, magazines etc to dispatch new technology to the Sri Lankan institute. Further, the relevant local authorities had modified the training programme year by year to suit the requirements of the German automobile products.

With regard to the structure of the training programme selected, the total duration is three years of which one year is for practical training. During the first year, trainees gain theoretical and practical knowledge on general fitting, machining, identifying components etc. During the second year they learn more deeply on automobile troubleshooting. The final year is completely on practical training at the workshop. The number of intake per year is 20 trainees. All of the trainees are absorbed to a specialized automobile workshop after successful completion of the programme.

Technical Training Institute C

The training institute established was established in late 1980s train automobile mechanics capable to handle new Japanese technology and to fulfil the requirements of this skill category of automobile industry. The training programme selected is developed by Japanese experts and local counterparts together. During the grant period, Japanese experts were attached to the Sri Lankan training institute to train local staff on automobile mechanics for a three year period. Further Japanese experts came to train local staff on auto electrical and automation during the next two years period. Local training officers were trained in Japan and in Malaysia under third country training programmes. By early 1990s the Japanese grant period elapsed.

With regard to the structure of the training programme selected, the total duration is three years. Out of the 36 months, 14 months apprentices receive theoretical as well as practical training at the institute whilst the balance 22 months are spent at industrial establishments connected with automobile engineering. During the programmes trainees can specialize in the fields of automobile mechanics, automobile electrician or automobile machinist. The number of intake per year is 120 trainees.

Technical Training Institute D

This training institute was established in mid 1990s in the field of maintenance of construction equipment. The training programme selected is designed and developed by

Japanese experts. Japan provided all buildings, equipment and other facilities. Experts were sent for a five year period to design and develop the training programme and to train local counterparts on the maintenance of construction equipment. The grant period elapsed in early 2000.

With regard to the structure of the training programme selected, the total duration is three years. Freshly recruited trainees follow three months theoretical and practical training at the institute during 1st, 2nd and 3rd years. During the first year, they learn basic workshop operations, component identification of the construction equipment and basic workshop theory. During their second year they learn disassemble and identification and reassemble of various components of the construction equipment with some advance workshop operation practice. During the third year, they learn trouble shooting and fault diagnosing techniques of the construction equipment using various faults diagnosing equipment. The balance 9 months of each year, they are attached to the industrial establishments for industrial training.

3.2. Framework of the Study

The aim of the investigation was to investigate technical training programmes that were initiated through technical corporation grants to assess appropriateness and effectiveness of the programmes. The specific objectives were to 1) investigate the way of delivery of training, 2) ways in which trainees develop their skills, 3) employers' satisfaction with the performance of the trainees who had successfully completed the training programmes and 4) recognition and demand for the technical training programmes. Given below is the *diagrammatic representation of the framework developed for the study*.

In the delivery of training programmes the programme content, the way of teaching theory and practice, audio-visual facilities for presentations, time allocations for practical and theory sessions, learning materials, library facilities are investigated. In how trainees develop their skills, way instructors facilitate trainees to develop skills during the stay in the training institution and after they went to the industry are investigated. In employers' satisfaction with the trainees, whether the institute provides quality service to obtain employers overall satisfaction on trainees' skill, subject knowledge, and abilities are investigated. Finally demand and recognition for training programmes are investigated, which represented the future success of the institute.

3.3. Methods of Data Collection and Analysis

When considering the four organizations, there are large variations in the number of passed out trainees who had successfully completed the training programmes. In addition, the relevant personnel such as training officers, demonstrators, and administrative officers in these organizations had changed since. Specially there is no person presently working at the training institute A, who was there during the grant period. For the study, it was decided to include all final year trainees of each selected training programme from each training institute; training officers who are presently working at the training institutes attached to selected training programmes; randomly selected trainees who had successfully completed the training and employed in various industrial establishments; randomly selected employers from the industrial establishments where these successfully completed trainees are employed in. Data was collected through questionnaires and interviews. Four questionnaires were developed to address the four sets of respondents.

In the analysis, responses of the four categories of respondents were weighted according to the number of respondents in each category and weighted percentage values were calculated.

4. Summary of Results and Discussion

Figures 1 to 4 show the summary of results by the main items investigated.

4.1. Way of Delivery of Training

As shown in Figure 1, the two training programmes selected from the A and B institutes obtained "best" or "better" responses for the way of delivery of training. The discussions revealed that training officers attached to two training programmes of German granted institutions were trained by German experts in Sri Lanka and in Germany. The similar responses were received from training officers attached to two training programmes of Japanese granted institutions C and D that they were too trained by Japanese experts in locally and in Japan. In the two training programmes of A and B institutes trainees undergo regular tests and those test marks are added to the final achievement. In the training programmes of C and D institutes, all tests are conducted after the end of the programme. The timeliness, proper working habits, safety measures, practicing rules etc. are properly practiced in both systems. Satisfactory level of physical facilities such as tools, diagnostic equipment, workshops, safety tools etc. had also been provided. In the four training programmes investigated from A, B, C, and D institutes, main attention had been drawn to the in-plant training during the training programme.

Figure 1 –Way of the delivery of training

4.2. How Trainees Develop their Skills

As shown in Figure 2, in the two training programmes of A and B institutes, trainees develop their skills much better than that of C and D institutes. The training programme of B institute offers properly designed theory and practical sessions to facilitate trainees for continuous skill development. All curriculum and practical sessions are clearly defined according to proper order in each year and curriculum is updated more often than that of other three institutes with the involvement of the German experts. The major barrier for the trainees who undergo selected four training programmes at the four institutions is that there is no clear path to upgrade their skills, knowledge and abilities after successful completion of the training programmes.

Figure 2 – How trainees develop their skills

4.3. Employers' Satisfaction with Employed Trainees who had Successfully Completed the Training

As shown in Figure 3, the majority of the employers' responses revealed that their satisfaction with the trainees from all the three selected training programmes from A, B, and C institutes are "high" or "moderate" except in institute D. Their theoretical knowledge at the point of the recruitment was up to desired level. But practical knowledge was not reached up to the required level. It was revealed that performance of

the employed trainees who had successfully completed the training depend not only on the training programme itself but also on their talents, attitudes, and behaviour. Some of the employers mentioned that employed trainees are not satisfied with the tasks and duties given to perform on the job as they have no opportunities to use the skill, knowledge and abilities gained from the technical institutes. The turnover rate of the employed trainees is considerably high as there are lot of job opportunities in the Middle Eastern countries. Except in few places, employers had not created clear promotion scheme or carrier path for the employed trainees. The most of the employers revealed that it was difficult to release them for further studies as they are front line workers.

Figure 3 – Employers' satisfaction with the employed trainees, who had successfully completed the training

4.4. Public Perception and Current Demand for the Training Programmes

As shown in Figure 4, the training programmes of institute A and B obtained “very high” and “high” perception for this aspect. It was revealed that annual demand for training programmes on automobile is high than that of for the maintenance of construction equipment. High demand for automobile programmes of the institutes A and B is due to the availability of job opportunities abroad especially in Middle Eastern countries due to the availability of German based automobile products there. However, the demand for automobile programme in the institute C is due to availability of job opportunities locally due to the availability of Japanese based automobile products here.

Figure 4: Public perception and current demand for the training programmes

5. Conclusions and Implications

According to the project proposals of all the four programmes and training institutes investigated, the fundamental reason for the establishment of the training institutes and the development of training programmes is to maintain and popularize German and Japanese products in Sri Lanka. With regard to the period of technical corporation grants, grant period of institutes A and B ranged from 8 to 15 years; this period was divided into several stages. In institutes C and D grant period ranged from 4 to 8 years. In all cases technology transfer was continuous during the assigned period. However, it was revealed that the systematic technology transfer during a longer period is the most success. Overall, findings led to conclude that in all the four technical training institutes, both donors and recipients mainly concerned with buildings, vehicles, machinery, etc. and less concerned with the training of trainers, technology upgrading channels, the arrangements for institute management procedures, etc. Through the grants, donors provided very expensive infrastructure facilities including buildings, lighting, air conditioning, equipment, etc. that require high investment to maintain the institutes.

All motor vehicles and spare parts are imported to the country. Thus, demand is high to get training in automobile field. The construction sector should play a crucial role at every stage of socioeconomic development of a country. Construction equipment incorporates systems such as electrical, hydraulic, and compressed air. The maintenance of such requires special knowledge and skills making the likely causes of poor mechanical operation of the construction equipment human-related due to inappropriate operation and a lack of proper maintenance. Thus there is a need to make effort to popularize the maintenance of construction equipment filed.

It should be noted however that, the results of the findings are based on the perception of four sets of respondents who filled the survey questionnaire and who participated in the interviews. Therefore, the validity of the findings rests on the accuracy of the respondents' perceptions. Further, the study was conducted using a sample of four specialized technical training institutions. Therefore, findings could not be generalized to all the third level training programmes conducted by Sri Lankan technical training institutions.

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